

TRIFFID

Autonomous Robotic Aid For increasing First responders efficiency

D1.1: Project reference manual and quality plan

Related tasks	Task T1.1: Project coordination Task T1.2: Technical management and quality assurance Task T1.5: Innovation management
Lead beneficiary	1 - HUA
Authors	Georgios Th. Papadopoulos (HUA), Adamantia Anna Rebolledo Chrysochoou (HUA)
Deliverable type	R - Document, report
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Status	Final
Due date	M3 - December-2024
Submission date	29/12/2024
Version	1.0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No.101168042. Content reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

List of contributors	
Contributing Partner	Contributors
HUA	Georgios Th. Papadopoulos
HUA	Adamantia Anna Rebolledo Chrysochoou
Reviewing Partner	Reviewers
UPC	Angel Santamaria Navarro
ITML	Chrysa Alexia

Document history			
Version	Date	Main author	Summary of changes
0.1	12/11/2024	HUA	Table of content creation
0.2	20/11/2024	HUA	Input for sections 1-9
0.3	22/11/2024	HUA	Integration of comments/edits provided by partner TEL
0.4	30/11/2024	HUA	Integration of comments/edits provided by internal reviewer partners UPC and ITML
1.0	29/12/2024	HUA	Production of final version of the deliverable

Executive summary

The current deliverable details the overall project management plan established for the TRIFFID project, serving as the project's reference manual, while specific guidelines for realizing quality assurance and risk management regarding the project's research & development results are provided. The defined management principles, guidelines, procedures and tools will be leveraged by the project coordinator to lead the implementation of the project efficiently and effectively.

In particular, the document initially describes the project governance plan, including the management structure, the roles of the various project bodies and the decision-making procedures. Additionally, a detailed definition of all required formal procedures (concerning meetings, project reviews, reporting and payments) is provided, accompanied by thorough analysis of all relevant collaboration tools and communication means that will be used for accomplishing the goals of the project. Particular attention is given to supporting the project activities with appropriate quality assurance mechanisms, including self-assessment pipelines, guidelines for deliverable preparation and procedures for deliverable internal evaluation. Moreover, a dedicated risk management methodology is detailed, including all necessary steps from risk identification and assessment to risk mitigation and tracking. Furthermore, initial guidelines regarding innovation management are also included, outlining key considerations regarding the approach to be followed and the addressing of relevant intellectual property rights issues.

The project management procedures presented in this report were established during the first months of the project based on best practices and long-standing procedures followed by the project coordinator (HUA), while in line with TRIFFID's contractual documents. These procedures may be revised in the future as per the needs of the project, and any changes will be made available to all partners through the project's communication and collaboration channels.

Table of Contents

Executive summary	4
Table of Contents.....	5
List of tables	8
List of figures.....	9
List of acronyms	10
1. Introduction.....	11
2. Project governance.....	12
2.1. Consortium management structure.....	12
2.2. Roles and responsibilities of project bodies.....	13
2.2.1. Project coordinator.....	13
2.2.2. Technical manager.....	14
2.2.3. Innovation manager	14
2.2.4. Dissemination manager.....	15
2.2.5. Project coordination committee	15
2.2.6. Work-package leaders.....	16
2.2.7. Ethics advisor.....	17
2.2.8. External advisory board	17
2.3. Decision-making and conflict resolution	18
2.3.1. Decision-making procedure	18
2.3.2. Conflict resolution rules.....	19
2.4. Key project contacts	19
3. Formal procedures	21
3.1. Meetings	21
3.1.1. Plenary meetings.....	21
3.1.2. Periodic teleconferences	22
3.1.3. Preparation of project meetings	22
3.1.4. Plenary meeting documentation.....	23
3.2. Project reviews	23
3.3. Reporting.....	24
3.3.1. Reporting to EC	24
3.3.2. Internal reporting	25
3.4. Payments	26

4.	Collaboration tools.....	28
4.1.	Workspace and repository.....	28
4.2.	Documentation.....	30
4.2.1.	Project logos.....	30
4.2.2.	Templates and naming conventions.....	30
4.3.	Software development.....	31
4.3.1.	Use of GitLab repository.....	31
4.3.2.	Two-headed software management.....	31
5.	Communication means.....	33
5.1.	Coordination address for mail delivery.....	33
5.2.	Communication tools.....	33
5.2.1.	Project website.....	33
5.2.2.	Mailing lists.....	33
5.2.3.	Audio and teleconference bridge.....	34
6.	Quality assurance.....	35
6.1.	Self-assessment.....	35
6.2.	Preparation of deliverables.....	36
6.3.	Deliverables and internal reviewers.....	36
7.	Risk management.....	39
7.1.	Risk methodology.....	39
7.2.	Risk identification.....	40
7.3.	Risk assessment and analysis.....	41
7.4.	Risk mitigation plan.....	42
7.5.	Risk mitigation plan implementation.....	42
7.6.	Risk tracking.....	42
7.7.	Risk registry.....	42
8.	Innovation management.....	45
8.1.	Rationale.....	45
8.2.	Approach.....	45
8.3.	Vision, objective, strategy, activities.....	45
8.3.1.	Innovation vision and objectives.....	45
8.3.2.	Strategy and activities.....	46
8.3.3.	Roles.....	48
8.4.	Intellectual property rights.....	49

8.5. Maturity level of generated innovations.....49

9. Conclusions.....51

List of tables

Table 1 Project coordination committee composition 16

Table 2 List of work-package leaders..... 17

Table 3 Timeline for finalizing dates and circulating meeting agenda 23

Table 4 Templates and naming conventions 30

Table 5 TRIFFID mailing lists 34

Table 6 Timeframe for deliverable preparation..... 36

Table 7 Deliverables and internal reviewers 37

Table 8 Responsibility assignment matrix for risk management..... 40

Table 9 Risk level likelihood..... 41

Table 10 Risk severity levels..... 41

Table 11 Qualitative assessment of identified risks 41

Table 12 Quantitative assessment of identified risks 42

Table 13 Risks identified during the grant preparation phase 43

List of figures

Figure 1 TRIFFID management bodies	12
Figure 2 Google Chat logo	28
Figure 3 Google Drive logo	28
Figure 4 TRIFFID online repository structure.....	29
Figure 5 Small-scale TRIFFID project logo	30
Figure 6 Full-scale TRIFFID project logo.....	30
Figure 7 GitLab logo	31
Figure 8 Software development flow	32
Figure 9 The “Plan-Do-Check-Act” (PDCA) iterative design and management method	35
Figure 10 Gantt chart with deliverable submission dates.....	38
Figure 11 Risk management lifecycle	39
Figure 12 Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale	50

List of acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statement
DM	Dissemination Manager
DoA	Description of the Action
EA	Ethics Advisor
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IM	Innovation Manager
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IS	Innovation Strategy
PC	Project Coordinator
PCC	Project Coordination Committee
PDCA	Plan-Do-Check-Act
PMO	Project Management Office
PO	Project Officer
PRM	Project Reference Manual
TL	Task Leader
TM	Technical Manager
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WP	Work-Package
WPL	Work-Package Leaders

1. Introduction

This document's primary goal is to serve as a source-guide for TRIFFID members to consult when conducting the daily management tasks of the project. In order to standardize every reporting, communication and documentation process used throughout the entire project, the goal is to compile all the data linked to management and operation tasks. Every work package and consortium partner may utilize this Project Reference Manual (PRM), which may be revised as needed throughout the project's development. The purpose of this document is unrelated to the project's technical advancement. The management framework and key procedures necessary to properly configure the project activities are established in this deliverable. There are no plans for this deliverable to be updated, though this document is a live document prone to changes if needed.

This deliverable establishes methods to ensure the quality of the procedures and documentation required, in order to help the partners understand the timing and responsibilities of the project. In order to make the right decisions and resolve conflicts as they arise during the project, this deliverable defines the coordination structures, communication tools and processes that must be followed.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

Section 2: The project governance structure is defined in detail, including the description of the various project bodies, their roles and the adopted decision-making procedures.

Section 3: This part details the formal procedures to be followed by TRIFFID, regarding the preparation of meetings, project reviews, official reports and payments, in accordance with the GA and CA specifications.

Section 4: This section describes the various collaboration tools that will be used by TRIFFID for the project implementation, including the online project repository, the available document templates and the software/code sharing infrastructure.

Section 5: An overview of the project's communication channels and tools utilized, regarding both internal to the project and external information exchange cases, is described in this section.

Section 6: This section details the quality assurance plan, including the procedures to be followed for deliverable preparation and internal review.

Section 7: An overview of the particular steps to be followed within TRIFFID regarding the identification, mitigation and tracking of risks is provided in this part.

Section 8: This section describes the approaches to be followed regarding the exploitation of innovation items generated by TRIFFID as well as the management of intellectual property right issues.

Section 9: This section concludes the document.

2. Project governance

This section provides a detailed explanation of the main organizational structure as well as a list of the consortium partners who will oversee-supervise the project's management and execution. The information on the relevant partner contacts, roles, and project bodies' scope will be known once the structure has been thoroughly described. In the Consortium Agreement (CA), duties and obligations are further identified and defined. However, the Project Coordination Committee (PCC) may decide to create new Task Forces and designate them with different responsibilities depending on how the project is carried out.

The project bodies will work to ensure that the tasks are completed successfully. Additionally, these organizations will work to ensure that any transversal issues, such as ethical concerns and innovation focus, are properly addressed.

2.1. Consortium management structure

The TRIFFID project will follow the management scheme presented below.

Figure 1 TRIFFID management bodies

The key management bodies of TRIFFID, as illustrated in Figure 1, are:

- Project Coordinator (PC)
- Technical Manager (TM)
- Innovation Manager (IM)
- Dissemination Manager (DM)
- Ethics Advisor (EA)
- External Advisory Board (EAB)
- Project Coordination Committee (PCC)
- Work-Package Leader (WPL)

2.2. Roles and responsibilities of project bodies

TRIFFID will employ a simple structure for decision making, where decisions are made at plenary level, by achieving consensus between the relevant partners. The Consortium Agreement (CA), which has been signed by all partners, defines all the rules and procedures for reaching consensus.

The Project Coordination Committee (PCC) is defined as the highest decision-making body, implementation and oversight is performed at Work-Package (WP) level.

2.2.1. Project coordinator

The **Project Coordinator (PC)** is responsible for overseeing the execution of the project and coordinating the various activities that will be carried out during its lifetime. Along with the WP leaders, the PC will be responsible for the proper use of resources, objectives' achievement and management of all project activities. In addition, the PC will have overall responsibility for the implementation of the project, ensuring quality, costs, and the planned delivery date. Furthermore, the PC will be the intermediary between the TRIFFID Consortium and the European Commission (EC) in all the necessary interactions to be carried out.

In terms of engagements with the other participants, the PC will preside over the PCC, serve as a conflict mediator in accordance with the CA's provisions, and have numerous interfaces with the project bodies in order to oversee and ensure the day-to-day operations of TRIFFID.

Therefore, the PC can be synthesized as the main contact point for the following entities:

- European Commission (EC)
 - Mainly with the Project Officer (PO) and through the SyGMA portal
 - Is in charge of requesting and verifying all official reporting
- Technical Manager (TM)
 - Manage the project's technical oversight
 - Hold important teleconferences to make tactical and strategic decisions
- Innovation Manager (IM)
 - Support the innovation process of the project in particular the generation of the primary innovative results and their readiness for exploitation and uptake actions and the discovery of potential secondary innovations
- Dissemination Manager (DM)
 - Support the dissemination process of the project, by defining the dissemination and communication strategies, while ensuring the meeting of timelines and commitment of all partners
- Work Package Leaders (WPL)
 - Maintain technical oversight of the project
 - Ensure resource efficiency
 - Monitor partners' commitment to project research objectives completion
 - Request status reports
- Ethics Advisor (EA)
 - Provide advice and suggestions on the following issues: a) The informed consent procedures, regarding FR/citizens captures for dataset creation, b) The gender and diversity issues in human-robot collaboration, and c) The human oversight in human/AI interaction

- External Advisory Board (EAB)
 - Serve as the consortium's point of contact with external experts
 - Advise on the overall process and advancements of the project

The PC, apart from overseeing every aspect of the project, must also keep track of the participants' execution of their responsibilities and ensure that the documents are delivered on schedule. The PC should manage the project's document repository and assure that the documentation is updated while also updating the mailing list for members' communication and share relevant information between the consortium and the funding authorities, since he/she is also responsible of organizing financial resources and committing to financial obligations. Finally, the PC must implement the formal procedures outlined in the GA and this document for the decision-making processes, delivering to the parties, upon request, official copies or originals of any documents in the coordinator's sole possession that are required for the presentation of claims by these parties and coordinate all partners by planning meetings and project review preparation processes.

In TRIFFID, the partner serving the role of the coordinator is HUA and the person in charge of PC is **Dr. Georgios Th. Papadopoulos**.

2.2.2. Technical manager

The **Technical Manager (TM)** will serve as the first PC deputy and action representative, as well as managing the activities related to action distribution. The TM is responsible for keeping constant communication with the WP leaders while supervising the technical completion of the assignments. Any technical issues that crop up throughout the project shall be reported to the PC and the PCC. The TM is in charge of coordinating real development with technical needs, goals, and high-tech standards across all TRIFFID technological duties and maintaining constant awareness of the project's technical status in order to report to higher levels, take action at lower levels, anticipate dangers, and make appropriate plans. Moreover, he/she must join the PCC and show up to all technical meetings and reviews and align the project's technical focus with the standards defined by the innovation manager. Finally, the TM is in charge of facilitating the coordination between the use cases easier and assisting the WPL in dissemination activities, along with aligning with the dissemination manager.

In TRIFFID, the partner serving the role of the technical manager is UPC, and the person in charge of TM is **Dr. Angel Santamaria Navarro**.

2.2.3. Innovation manager

The project's exploitable outcomes will be properly protected and exposed through the coordination of actions by the **Innovation Manager (IM)**. Along with distribution efforts, this entails developing and implementing an Innovation Strategy (IS) and supporting and advising the partners during the development phase of their innovation items to ensure that they are ready to enter the exploitation and take-up phase. The definition of joint exploitation agreements and other legal instruments, as well as formal IPR management that supports open-source licensing, are used to protect the results. The PCC may establish an **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)** board, presided over by the IM, to evaluate all decisions pertaining to IPR, based on IPR ownership, and to provide recommendations for the definition of access rights and use of findings, including licensing.

At the consortium level, **Mr. Dimitris Eleftheriou** from ITML serves in the capacity of innovation manager and will report on IPR and innovation in general.

More information about the scope of action of the IM in TRIFFID can be found in Section 8 of this document.

2.2.4. Dissemination manager

The project's **Dissemination Manager (DM)** will define TRIFFID's dissemination and communication strategies, while at the same time overseeing the meeting of relevant timelines and commitment of all partners. The dissemination plan will cross all WPs for the entire duration of the project. Additionally, the DM will pay particular attention to community building and clustering with relevant initiatives activities. The latter will aim at building an expanded community of relevant application and scientific stakeholders, so as to communicate the TRIFFID vision, to obtain valuable feedback and to boost the potential for further synergies and collaborations. Additionally, clustering with existing H2020/Horizon Europe projects, networks or platforms, as well as European associations, will be prioritized.

At the consortium level, **Mr. Ioannis Kefaloukos** from HMU serves in the capacity of the dissemination manager.

2.2.5. Project coordination committee

The **Project Coordination Committee (PCC)** bears the final saying over all financial matters, changes or additions to the consortium agreement or action objectives, and general consortium regulations. The project coordinator serves as its chair.

The work will be guided by their coordination tasks, which will result in efficient communication between all partners. The PCC's duties and responsibilities are as follows:

- To organize the PCC meetings, including the agenda development, proposed decisions, and minutes preparation.
 - Similarly, the PCC meetings' decisions are guaranteed to be executed.
- To seek agreement from consortium partners on significant concerns that emerge throughout the project.
 - In the absence of agreement, PCC shall supervise the implementation of the voting processes, decision-making processes, and dispute resolution processes outlined in the consortium agreement.
- To keep track of the project's efficient execution, particularly with relation to schedules, CA alignment, and contact (through the PC) with the EC.
- To gather information on the project's progress on a regular basis, coordinating the development of reports for both internal review and official reviews.
- To come to an agreement on the GA amendments that will be submitted to the EC.
- To accept significant project changes and discuss with the EC on key issues regarding the addition and removal of partners and financial management.

Other characteristics of the PCC body shall be:

- To ensure this statement, representatives of all TRIFFID consortium partners must be present at the PCC.

- Any partner may call a PCC meeting to discuss a particular matter as long as it does not relate to a task, a WP, or fundamental management skills.
- All PCC members, as shown in Table 1, are required to attend each meeting. Every participant in the project is formally invited to attend as a listener, but only the representatives mentioned for each entity will have the authority to cast votes on behalf of the partner.

The composition of this committee has been considered during the development of this document, and at this point, it will be represented by the following individuals:

Table 1 Project coordination committee composition

Name	Partner	Contact
Georgios Th. Papadopoulos	HUA	G.Th.Papadopoulos@hua.gr
Ioannis Kefaloukos	HMU	g.kefaloukos@pasiphae.eu
Angel Santamaria Navarro	UPC	angel.santamaria@upc.edu
Eugenio Mantovani	VUB	Eugenio.Mantovani@vub.be
Ondřej Severa	UWB	osevera@ntis.zcu.cz
Andrea Orlandini	CNR	andrea.orlandini@istc.cnr.it
Christian Resch	DCNA	christian.resch@dena.at
Dimitris Drakoulis	TEL	dimitris@telesto.gr
Chrysa Alexia	ITML	calexia@itml.gr
Philippe Besson	PUI	pbesson@pompiers-urgence.org
Robbert Heinecke	GB	robbert.heinecke@nipv.nl
Sofoklis Mavroftas	HFC	smavroftas@gmail.com
Evangelos Sakkas	ROE	e.sakkas@php.gov.gr

2.2.6. Work-package leaders

All project partners involved in the work packages will complete the relevant tasks, and the appropriate WP leaders will manage these tasks. Monitoring the status of the assigned work package is the responsibility of each work package leader. While the technical manager must carry out the technical control along with WPL, the project coordinator will be in charge of overseeing the project's overall management progress.

The responsibilities of the **Work Package Leaders (WPL)** are:

- Monitor work progress and performance, including:
 - Ensure that information flows horizontally to other WPs
 - Report any pertinent technical difficulties to the technical manager
 - Report any pertinent management issues to the project coordinator (and PCC, if necessary)
 - Monitor the progress of the WP in achieving its goals by engaging with task leaders
 - Ensure compliance with TRIFFID's global objectives
- Execution of tasks within the WP
- Set up regular teleconferences to track the WP's progress. At first, it is assumed that all WPs will be subject to a monthly teleconference rule. If necessary, each WPL will decide whether to schedule additional teleconferences
- Participate in and maintain close contact with the TM to make sure that all project WPs are coordinated and technically aligned
- Periodically update the plenary teleconferences on the WP's status
- Report the status of the WP at any time upon the PC's, TM's, or PCC's request

- Create reports upon PC’s request for official reporting in support of the periodic review
- Serve as a channel for communication between the task leaders and the PC/TM:
 - Each WP has been divided into a number of tasks that have already been designated by task leaders, who serve as coordinators of task execution and are accountable to their respective work-package leader. PCC or WPs can establish/define ad hoc activities and their leaders.
 - Similar to how work is organized at the WP level, tasks are managed by corresponding task leaders, along with task partners and contributors of the specific project deliverables.

Table 2 List of work-package leaders

WP	Name	Partner	Contact
WP1	Georgios Th. Papadopoulos	HUA	G.Th.Papadopoulos@hua.gr
WP2	Robbert Heinecke	GB	robbert.heinecke@nipv.nl
WP3	Angel Santamaria Navarro	UPC	angel.santamaria@upc.edu
WP4	Jorgen Cani	HUA	cani@hua.gr
WP5	Christian Resch	DCNA	christian.resch@dcna.at
WP6	Dimitris Drakoulis	TEL	dimitris@telesto.gr
WP7	Ioannis Kefaloukos	HMU	g.kefaloukos@pasiphae.eu
WP8	Adamantia Anna Rebolledo Chrysochoou	HUA	adamantia.reb@hua.gr

2.2.7. Ethics advisor

As detailed in deliverable D8.1 “OEI - Requirement No. 1”, the responsibility of the TRIFFID **Ethics Advisor (EA)** is to provide advice on the following issues:

- The informed consent procedures, regarding first-responders/citizens captures for Dataset #DS2 “Human action/motion/gesture data” and #DS3 “Human behavioral studies” of the project
- The gender and diversity issues in human-robot collaboration, putting particular attention on whether female voices are less recognized
- The human oversight in human/AI interaction, where it needs to be made clear that decisions are only taken by humans, not by AI systems.

The responsibility of the EA is to provide advise either orally or in writing. The EA’s advice will be sought ahead of the submission of deliverables D1.4-D1.6 “Ethical framework, societal impact assessment and innovation report, version 1-3”, due in May 2025, March 2026 and September 2027, respectively, and reported therein.

The EA of TRIFFID is **Dr. Andrew P. Rebera**, affiliated with the Royal Military Academy (Brussels, Belgium) and the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (Leuven, Belgium).

2.2.8. External advisory board

The **External Advisory Board (EAB)** will have representatives from the academic community, big business, SMEs, and standardization organizations. The EAB’s duties will include giving input on action outputs and making recommendations for alignment with the evolving SotA of concepts and technologies relevant to action activities.

Generally speaking, EAB members are expected to offer advice on the TRIFFID industrial and technological roadmap, input and feedback, technical, moral, and legal guidance, suggestions for links with pertinent interest groups outside of TRIFFID, facilitation of information about market trends for technology and business models, and encouragement of interactions with other projects and initiatives.

More particular, TRIFFID intends to plan periodic meetings in order to direct EAB members' engagement. This strategy will depend on any mobility and travel budget limitations. Any costs concerning travelling for this purpose will be reimbursed as long as the project coordinator is informed (as it is indicated in the GA). If it is impossible to hold the actual meetings, substitute virtual meetings will be organized, to which EAB members will also be invited. Additionally, more EAB interventions are anticipated to occur during the project in the form of virtual teleconferences.

The members of the EAB represent a comprehensive cross-section of stakeholders and interested sectors in TRIFFID, including organizations whose mission is to address all forms of physical disasters. The structure of the members has been established using those agreed-upon procedures. Technical, industrial, and academic standards have been used to identify specific individuals who may potentially make important contributions to TRIFFID. As experts in their fields, EAB will contribute significantly to the development of the TRIFFID project.

Thus, specialists for the main application domains of TRIFFID are part of the initial list of External Advisory Board members:

- Mr. Gerald Czech, Strategy and Science Coordination, Upper Austrian Fire Brigade Headquarter (gerald.czech@feuerwehr.or.at)
- Dr. Efstratios Gavves, Assoc. Professor, University of Amsterdam (E.Gavves@uva.nl)
- Dr. Panayiotis S Kolios, Ass. Professor, KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, University of Cyprus (kolios.panayiotis@ucy.ac.cy)
- Mr. Ilias Mitsoulas, Senior CBRNe Expert, Resilience Advisors Network (ilias.mitsoulas@resilienceadvisors.eu)
- Mr. Sebastiaan Star, Fire Captain, Safety Region Rotterdam-Rijnmond (Sebastiaan.Star@vr-rr.nl)
- Mr. Panagiotis Sarigiannidis, Professor, University of Western Macedonia (psarigiannidis@uowm.gr)

It needs to be noted that the composition of the EAB will be revisited during the project lifetime, if needed.

2.3. Decision-making and conflict resolution

TRIFFID's goal is that there is consensus-based decision-making among all project partners working at all levels. However, it is likely that partners won't always agree on certain issues, in which case a dispute resolution process would need to be used. For this reason, a decision-making process and dispute resolution guidelines are offered to help, if necessary, make the right decisions.

2.3.1. Decision-making procedure

Below are some guidelines for making decisions and some viewpoints to take into account:

1. The work-package leader should be consulted first when a management issue may occur, followed by the PC and, if necessary, the PCC via a formal session.
2. Should a technical issue occur within a WP, the task leader will address it after discussing with the WPL, who may need to play a significant role in the process. If the problem cannot be resolved, it may be scaled up to the PCC and PC.
3. The PC will be the one to immediately take charge of handling any potential financial issues.

4. If an IPR issue does occur, it will be handled by IM and, if still not resolved, by IM and the PC. A PCC session might ultimately be organized in the event that vote or consensus is required.

Alternatively, specific voting principles can be used, if necessary, in cases when consensus cannot be reached. The CA will outline the Project Coordination Committee (PCC) voting process, which will be based on the qualified majority principle (two thirds of the consortium) and the proper handling of high-level management issues will be supervised by this committee. Alternatively, at the work-package level, decisions are determined by consensus and, if that isn't possible, by the qualified majority principle (two thirds), with each partner having one vote.

2.3.2. Conflict resolution rules

When the interests and viewpoints of the various participants diverge to the point where discrepancies cannot be addressed on their own, a conflict results. In this situation, it is necessary to swiftly and unquestionably resolve the issue in order to ensure proper and perpetual execution of the project.

From lower to higher action levels (from task to WP level and from WP to action level bodies, TM and PC in that sequence, and a PCC session if necessary), conflict resolution will take place, with the corresponding action leaders serving as mediators. The PCC will form a special working group when resolving a conflict presenting unique challenges. Conflicts shall ultimately be resolved in accordance with the GA. Conflicts that cannot be settled using these guidelines shall be handled in accordance with the CA's requirements.

The first conflict resolution tool that should be used in a disagreement is a special task/work-package meeting that attendance at that special meeting is required of all parties participating in the task/work-package. Then, the second level is that all personnel from all partners who are accountable for the project's progress attend the special PCC meeting. Conflicts should typically be resolved at the latest during this project management meeting.

The order of documents to be considered, whenever a conflict develops, is worth mentioning as well. A responsible party must study the following resources below, which define the project's governance following this specific priority scale (in this strict order):

1. EU Grant Agreement 101168042 (GA).
2. Consortium Agreement that is signed by all TRIFFID consortium partners.
3. Deliverable D1.1 "Project reference manual and quality plan" (this document).

The EU Grant Agreement (GA), both Annex I and Annex II, also known as the Description of the Action (DoA), and the Consortium Agreement (CA), specify the general guidelines for the project's execution. The EU requirements for project implementation and documentation are not replaced by the project reference manual. The preceding order of documents should be followed if there are any possible inconsistencies.

2.4. Key project contacts

All necessary contacts for the TRIFFID project can be found in Table 1 and Table 2 provided above.

TRIFFID's repository will include a constantly updated database with various details, in addition to the provided tables. It must contain the PCC, as well as his/her alternate; WP; task and activity leaders. The organizations that handle administrative and financial issues (reports), as well as a directory with the

names, contact information, and primary job duties of everyone directly involved in the project. It must also include the participation in the various mailing lists and events that are scheduled and a thorough listing of all partners' main contacts.

The data will be updated as necessary over the course of the project. Data protection directives will be implemented at national and European level, and the directory will only be accessed through invitations and identity control/verification.

3. Formal procedures

3.1. Meetings

To make good use of time and resources, the TRIFFID project meetings will mostly take place as plenary events that combine meetings of multiple project bodies at various levels. They might coincide with local impact creation events (e.g., conferences or workshops).

Meetings will be scheduled three to four times a year, depending on the demands of the project. Individual meetings for specific groups will also be organized as needed (for example, at the WP level, code-camps, etc.).

Unpredictable conditions or circumstances beyond project control may force cancellations of physical meetings and to organization of virtual events.

3.1.1. Plenary meetings

Representatives from each partner should be present at the plenary meetings. Physically, the plenary meetings will take place at a location that has already been chosen by the consortium. Depending on the participation in the tasks and activities discussed at the conference, each partner may send one or more participants.

By project start a kick-off meeting takes place. The TRIFFID kick-off meeting was held online on the 1st and 2nd of October 2024 with the following issues on the agenda:

- Project presentation
- Consortium partners presentation
- Project management procedures presentation
- One slot for each WP
- Presentation of HORIZON EUROPE administrative framework, presented by the PO
- Project's corporative image decision and update
- Technical WPs presentation and overview
- Conclusion, ongoing tasks and next steps

Internal plenary meetings will be held throughout the project. These meetings, which will primarily take the form of virtual teleconferences, will track the project's progress, the achievement of milestones, and the status of the tasks. In light of these developments, it is anticipated that pertinent decisions will be made.

The PC will be in charge of planning the agenda, controlling the flow of time, setting up invites to outside guests (such as EAB and participants from other EU-funded projects), and presiding over the entire meeting. The hosting partner will take care of venue reservations and co-located events, like community meets with stakeholders. Plenary meetings are anticipated to be held at various places, hosted by the local partner.

These sessions, which include the whole consortium and the entire project, will provide enough time in order to share administrative data, as well as technical issues relevant to the interactions between and within work packages.

Various project concerns will be discussed in plenary meetings, including the review of the project's current overall status, upcoming milestones and unfinished advances. There must be one slot for reviewing upcoming administrative and financial tasks and one slot for each active WP. If necessary, designated timeslots for committee meetings must be included. The following requirements must be met for the organized committees to meet and schedule the plenary meetings: i) the Project Coordination Committee (PCC), the PCC is presided over by the PC and meets twice a year or as needed by its members, and ii) the External Advisory Board (EAB), and there will be multiple AB meetings. Additional feedback may, however, be solicited at crucial points in the action. Last, but not least, there must be a discussion on the conclusions and next steps, so as on other issues that may have occurred.

Plenary meetings will have a long-term strategy presented by the project coordinator, unless undue, i.e., extreme events break out.

On the other hand, dedicated technical meetings will be scheduled as needed by the participants to analyze or address a technical issue that is being developed for the project. Only those working groups linked to the technical development under analysis will be asked to participate, since participation of other partners is not necessary. These meetings can take on several formats based on the nature of the request and the primary activity of the participants, including sessions for decision-making or programming as well as discussions of technical ideas, like architecture or implementation. These meetings may occur separately or as distinct threads of the event, as well as inside larger plenary meetings. The TM will be in charge of organizing the agenda, supervising the meetings and supporting participating partners.

3.1.2. Periodic teleconferences

At all levels, when necessary, audio/web conferences will be organized to ensure the continuity of all events. Regular teleconferences can be any of the following, depending on the attendees and the meeting's objectives:

- Plenary teleconference meetings, once a month
 - These teleconference sessions must be attended by all partners
 - According to the guidelines outlined in the CA, decisions made in these teleconferences shall be legally binding
- WP teleconference meetings once a month, while different periodicities maybe determined by WPs
 - Attendance is required for partners who are working in that WP
 - In these sessions, task leaders will be required to report on the status of their work

3.1.3. Preparation of project meetings

The host of each meeting is also responsible for organizing the planned meeting. This entails setting up a suitable venue and the essential tools for the conference, as well as communicating the preferred accommodation options to the other participating partners.

The PC or TM will be in charge of setting the agenda and serving as the meeting's chair, depending on the type of meeting.

The organizing chairman must keep in mind and send notifications of the meeting's date well in advance and is in control of the creation and submission of the suggested agenda and meeting goals, while adhering to the deadlines shown in Table 3. Moreover, the organizer is in charge of limiting the topics

of conversation to reasonable time slots and meeting the timetable with a certain level of precision, while addressing all of the important subjects on the agenda. The chairman is responsible for moderating interventions and ensuring that each participant, regardless of experience, role, or language proficiency, gets the opportunity to voice their view. Whenever it is required, breaks must be taken (either planned or impromptu). The PC serves as the chairman of all plenary meetings. The TM serves as the chairman of all technical meetings. The PCC chairman corresponds to the PC. All relevant parties will receive the meeting agenda at least one week prior to the meeting.

Table 3 Timeline for finalizing dates and circulating meeting agenda

Type of meeting	Deadline for noticing the days	Deadline for sending the agenda
Physical plenary meeting (includes physical PCC session)	45 days	21 days
Extraordinary PCC session (normally virtual)	15 days	10 days
Plenary teleconference meeting	Periodically every month. Any change must be noticed 4 days in advance.	7 days
Periodic teleconference Meeting (e.g., WP, task)	Periodicity arranged internally. Any change must be noticed 4 days in advance.	3 days
Extraordinary teleconference meeting	2 days	1 day

3.1.4. Plenary meeting documentation

The meeting's agenda must be created, circulated, and stored in accordance with the timeframe specified in Table 3. These tasks must be completed on schedule and properly by the corresponding chairman.

The meeting's minutes must be written up within ten calendar days. The respective chairman will once more be in charge of creating the minutes. These minutes need to be brief but clear, outlining any decisions or pertinent statements made during the meeting.

The WP leaders are responsible for providing minutes for their respective WP meetings, while the PC is in charge of compiling the complete meeting minutes and recording various project-level discussions and decisions, including those from PCC and TM, during plenary meetings. The TRIFFID repository will host the meeting minutes and make them available for download. If no member sends a written objection to the chairperson regarding the veracity of the proposed minutes within 15 calendar days of receiving the minutes, they are deemed accepted.

3.2. Project reviews

There will be two project reviews, one around M18 and the other around M36. These meetings' precise timing and venue will be decided at least three months in advance with the PO. The PO will designate professionals to serve as reviewers at the conference. The PC will oversee and organize the preparation and submission of technical and financial reports of the project, along with deviations and corrective actions, prior to the meeting. Each partner is required to explain the costs incurred throughout the evaluation period. Following the meeting, the EC provides the PC with a report assessing the project's

development. The TRIFFID partners will be in charge of the demonstrations and presentations, which were already planned and approved by the PCC. The PC will create the agenda and assist the WP leaders (and all designated presenters) in preparing for the meeting, while taking the PCC's consensus into account. The PC will do so by creating the agenda for the meeting, where the review will be discussed, and support the WP leaders for the organization of the meeting, i.e., manage attendance-related details, such as making sure all partners have registered, act as host for all review presentations and make sure to record each presentation's minutes. Finally, the PC must send the report from the EC review to all partners.

3.3. Reporting

3.3.1. Reporting to EC

The technical and financial reports outlined in this section must be submitted by the coordinator to the European Commission (EC). These reports, which also include payment requests, must be created using the templates and formats offered by the electronic exchange system.

3.3.1.1. Periodic report

Following the conclusion of each reporting period, the coordinator is required to submit a periodic report within 60 days:

- Reporting period 1: from month 1 to month 18
- Reporting period 2: from month 19 to month 36

Both the technical and financial reports must be included in the report.

3.3.1.1.1. Technical report

An explanation of the work done by the recipients will formulate the technical reporting.

- A summary of the deliverables and milestones that have been reached in relation to the tasks' goals. The justifications for the discrepancies between the work that was expected to be done and what was actually done must be included in this report. The report must include information on how the findings were used and disseminated as well as a list of communication actions.
- A summary that the EC will publish.
- The responses to the "questionnaire", which addressed topics related to the implementation of the tasks and its effects on the economy and society, particularly in light of the Horizon Europe key performance indicators and the monitoring criteria.

3.3.1.1.2. Financial report

The financial report includes the following:

- An "Individual financial statement" from every partner for the relevant reporting period. The eligible costs (actual expenses, unit costs, and flat-rate costs) for each budget category must be specified in the individual financial statement. The beneficiaries are required to disclose all eligible expenses, even if they exceed the budgeted amounts for actual, unit, and flat-rate expenses. The European Commission will not take into consideration any amounts that are not disclosed in the

individual financial statement. The periodic financial report for the following reporting period may contain an individual financial statement that wasn't submitted for a given reporting period. The receipts for the action must also be mentioned in the individual financial statements from the most recent reporting period. Every beneficiary must attest that the information given is accurate, complete, and dependable, that the declared expenses are allowable, and that adequate records and supporting documentation can be produced upon request or in the course of checks, reviews, audits and investigations. Finally, each and every receipt should have been reported (for the last reporting period).

- An explanation of how resources were used, as well as details on each beneficiary's usage of subcontractors and in-kind donations from third parties, for the relevant reporting period.
- A "periodic summary financial statement", generated automatically by the electronic exchange system that combines the individual financial statements for the relevant reporting period and, for Reporting Period 1 only, includes the request for interim payment.

3.3.1.2. Final report

The coordinator shall deliver the final report within 60 days of the conclusion of the previous reporting period in addition to the periodic report for that time period.

Both the technical and the financial report must be included in the final report.

3.3.1.2.1. Final technical report

An overview of the findings, as well as their use and distribution, must be included in the technical portion of the final report.

- The task's results and conclusions, their evaluation and dissemination
- The task's socio-economic effects

3.3.1.2.2. Final financial report

The financial section of the final report must include:

- A "final summary financial statement", generated automatically by the electronic exchange system. It should consolidate the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and include a request for payment of the balance.
- If a beneficiary receives more than 430.000€ of EU contribution, a Certificate on the Financial Statement (CFS) needs to be provided.

3.3.2. Internal reporting

Partners in TRIFFID agree to submit their activities on a regular basis in order to carry out high-quality monitoring. The suggested internal reporting structure is based on two main categories, the financial and technical reporting.

Financial reporting: A summary of the resources used during the course of the six-month period for project monitoring purposes, including an estimate of the time spent on each activity by each employee and the major eligible expenditures made during that time. Any anticipated variation in the amount of work or costs anticipated for the following interval must also be submitted. To track the actual effort divergence from internal resource planning, PC shall provide a template for the gathering of this report.

All partners have access to the template in a specified folder in the documents repository, which has been provided by the PC.

Technical reporting: A list of the tasks completed during the course of six months must be submitted. Partners shall submit the report to the PC by the first week of the month after the period. All assets and a structure to assure accurate tracking of the work done, directed by follow-up calls must be included in the report. That document will adhere to a template that the PC will offer at the start of the project and the partners can find the template in a specified folder in the documents repository, which was provided by the PC.

All inputs will be compiled by the PC and will produce, every six months, reports for each WP and globally for the project. This control measure will assist in understanding the project status and implementing corrective actions if required. The PC will use the data collected as part of this internal reporting as input to create the periodic reports that will be generated for the official reviews as updates on the project's progress.

3.4. Payments

The funding payments will be organized and carried out in TRIFFID in accordance with the following rules:

- **Pre-financing:** The goal is to give the recipients a cushion. Up until the balance is paid, it remains the property of the EU. Pre-financing payments will be made in an amount equal to 80% of total project expenses (**€4,098,690.00**). The pre-financing payment will be made by the EC to the coordinator within 30 days, starting either from the date the GA enters into effect or, at the latest, from 10 days prior to the action's commencement date. The European Commission (EC) holds back from the pre-financing payment an amount equal to 5% of the maximum grant amount, i.e., **€204,934.50**. An amount of **€2,151,812.25** is to be distributed among the partners.
- **Interim payments:** Interim payments are used to cover qualified expenses incurred during the relevant reporting periods for carrying out the action. Within 90 days of receiving the periodic report, the EC will pay the coordinator the sum owing as interim payment. Payment is contingent on the periodic report's approval. Its endorsement does not signify acceptance of the content's compliance, authenticity, completeness, or accuracy.

The following steps are used by the EC to determine the amount payable as an interim payment:

- Application of the reimbursement rates: The rate(s) of reimbursement are applied to the eligible expenditures (actual costs, unit costs, and flat-rate costs) reported by the beneficiaries and authorized by the EC for the relevant reporting period.
- The total pre-financing and interim payments cannot be more than 90% of the specified maximum grant amount. "Prefinancing and earlier interim payments" will be used to determine the maximum amount of the interim payment.
- **Final payments:** Payment is contingent upon the final report's approval. Its clearance does not mean that its content is in accordance with standards of compliance, authenticity, completeness, or correctness. The remaining qualified expenditures incurred by the beneficiaries for the action's implementation are partially reimbursed by the payment of the balance. The EC will collect technical and financial data from all partners for each payment (aside from pre-financing), in order to assess the payment's compliance with the GA work plan and applicable rules. The EC will send

approval in response to this request or carry out the necessary corrective actions. The equivalent sum will be distributed to each partner by HUA once the corresponding reports have been approved by the European Commission. The payment of the remaining balance takes the form of a recovery if the total of prior payments exceeds the total amount of the grant. The Commission will pay the remaining balance within 90 days of receiving the final report if the total of earlier payments is less than the final award amount. The Commission determines the sum owed by subtracting the total of pre-financing and interim payments (if any) already made from the grant's total amount.

The global consideration is that the PC (HUA) will receive the payments and will then promptly administer the money to the beneficiaries on time.

4. Collaboration tools

Consortium partners will have access to collaboration tools that will be used to provide management information services, enable effective work and communication at various levels, and support all controlling actions. Mailing lists, repositories, web spaces, an audio/video conferencing bridge, and carefully chosen project management and reporting tools are just a few of the technologies that HUA will initially setup.

4.1. Workspace and repository

After discussion within the TRIFFID consortium, the daily operations of TRIFFID will be mostly handled by respective Google services, namely **Google Drive** and **Google Chat**. HUA's infrastructure is based on corresponding Google services; so, significant and useful characteristics (e.g., creation of mailing lists, online repositories of increased capacity, reinforced security measures, etc.) are available at no additional cost and will be used in the context of TRIFFID. In order to maximize data/communication security and to adhere to ethical and quality standards, access to all communication services is password protected and strict/periodic access control is applied.

Figure 2 Google Chat logo

Google Chat: This will enable the creation of collaborative workspaces and powerful/convenient group chats/messaging-channels, in order to facilitate partner discussions on several key project activities/topics. A critical advantageous characteristic of this approach is that the history of each created chat will be easily accessible/documentated for future revisits.

Figure 3 Google Drive logo

Google Drive: A dedicated online document repository, termed "Project TRIFFID" was created for the needs of the project. The link to the repository and access was provided only to verified participants of the consortium. The online repository is expected to play a significant role in the project's everyday operations, because it will be utilized for file sharing, document editing, and versioning. The project

coordinator will be responsible for making backup copies and updating the repository as necessary to prevent data loss.

Regarding the online repository setup, a folder structure that must be followed has been established. This framework must be followed by all partners to guarantee proper document access and storage, as follows:

- **Root folder (“Project TRIFFID”)**
 - **Meetings:** All meeting-related information (agenda, minutes, and presentations) will be stored here in sub-folders. Additionally, there will be virtual teleconferences like the monthly plenary telcos that will be considered meetings in this regard.
 - **Official documentation:** All information that has been rendered legally binding for the project before the EC. This will include documents like the GA, the CA, and the action’s Gantt chart. A sub-folder will incorporate the most recent iterations of the deliverables that have previously been sent to the EC via the SyGMa platform.
 - **Reviews:** All materials and documents to be included in the periodic reports, as well as any other relevant information; this will be organized into separate RP1 (reporting period #1) and RP2 (reporting period #2) folders.
 - **Risk registry:** This will include a spreadsheet (and possible relevant materials) that will detail all identified project risks, along with corresponding mitigation plans and actions taken.
 - **Supporting documentation:** You can use this folder as a dumping ground for any pertinent files that all partners might find helpful. This folder was first made with the following subdirectories:
 - **Dissemination materials:** All documents and materials used for dissemination purposes, e.g., project presentations, brochures, etc.
 - **Project logos:** All versions of high-resolution project logos.
 - **Templates:** All project templates to be followed for preparing deliverables, deliverable review reports, presentations, meeting agendas, meeting minutes, etc.
 - **Contacts list:** A spreadsheet containing all participants’ contact information
 - **Mailing lists:** A spreadsheet detailing all project created mailing lists and the respective participants included in each list
 - **Work packages:** Location where all project working documentation and materials are stored and organized by WP leaders.

Figure 4 TRIFFID online repository structure

4.2. Documentation

4.2.1. Project logos

Two versions of TRIFFID project logos have been created, namely a small- and a full-scale one. Both logos are provided in low- and high-resolution versions. The logos are available in the “Project TRIFFID\Supporting documentation\Project logos” folder in the online repository in raster format with transparency. Every TRIFFID document that is published and every communication or dissemination activity carried out within its purview must include this image logo.

Figure 5 Small-scale TRIFFID project logo

Figure 6 Full-scale TRIFFID project logo

4.2.2. Templates and naming conventions

A specific process has been established by the TRIFFID consortium for the production of the various documents of the project. In particular, Table 4 summarizes the main templates that have been created for TRIFFID, along with their respective naming conventions that have been adopted. The templates are available in the “Project TRIFFID\Supporting documentation\Templates” folder in the online repository, include guidelines regarding the preparation of each document type and are available in MS Office format.

Table 4 Templates and naming conventions

Document type	Naming convention
Deliverable	TRIFFID_deliverable-[Name]
Internal deliverable evaluation report	TRIFFID_deliverable-[Name]_evaluation_PXX-[partner acronym]
Financial report	TRIFFID_financial_report Mx-My_PXX-[partner acronym]
Technical report	TRIFFID_technical_report Mx-My_PXX-[partner acronym]
Meeting agenda	TRIFFID_meeting_agenda YYYYMMDD
Meeting minutes	TRIFFID_meeting_minutes YYYYMMDD

4.3. Software development

In the GA, guidelines for the creation of code and software are already provided. The WP leaders will be in charge of selecting the best tools or frameworks to implement their work. However, certain elements and technologies have already been identified that are suggested for all TRIFFID software development. The following software development choices/recommendations have been formulated at the current project development stage (and will be further refined later on).

4.3.1. Use of GitLab repository

GitLab is a web-based Git repository that provides free open and private repositories, issue-following capabilities, and wikis. It is a complete DevOps platform that enables developers to perform all required tasks in a project, ranging from project planning and source code management to monitoring and security. According to preliminary discussions, TRIFFID will make use of this platform, developing appropriate repositories for the various component development needs.

Figure 7 GitLab logo

4.3.2. Two-headed software management

The usage of distinct technologies to establish a two-headed software management will be adopted in TRIFFID. In response to the following schema, the division would act:

- Basic resources (facilitating coordinated development):
 - Gogs: Front-end tool for leveraging the git methodology to publish code in a repository
 - Docker: A software program that enables virtualization in containers for the specific execution of isolated operating systems or software tools independent of the host machine
- Supplementary tools (closely related to processes, but not necessary for coding):
 - Slack: A tool for collaborative work that allows for file sharing, conversation, and other features to support coordinated team growth
 - JIRA: A web-based project management solution targeted particularly at agile software development and integration, as well as requirements monitoring and compilation

The aforementioned tools will be available for TRIFFID and WP leaders will be able to choose whether to use them or not, according to their needs and requirements. A practical development flow for technical software activities in TRIFFID should resemble the one illustrated in Figure 8, taking into account the nature and function of every instrument that will be accessible for this style of management.

The overall software management is expected to adopt the following developing steps:

- Iterative coding and versioning using Git techniques
- Continuous integration
- Process automation with Jenkins CI assistant
- Publishing the code
- Connecting and syncing the updates with the other tools

- Making the binaries publicly available (Nexus)
- Checking the code's quality (SonarQube)
- Informing working teams of the status of the developments (Slack and communication tools, such as mail service)

Figure 8 Software development flow

5. Communication means

5.1. Coordination address for mail delivery

The following is the postal address for mail delivery to the PC:

HUA

Harokopio University of Athens
Department of Informatics & Telematics
9, Omirou Str.
GR 177 78, Tavros, Attiki, Greece
In attend. of: Ass. Prof. Georgios Th. Papadopoulos

The PC must be contacted for all discussions with the European Commission. Whether the communication is private or public is up to the sender. All other partners are informed when a partner requests to communicate with the European Commission in a non-confidential manner through the project coordinator. A partner must notify the project coordinator if he/she wishes to communicate with the European Commission in a private manner; the other partners will not be made aware of the communication.

5.2. Communication tools

Several tools will be used by the TRIFFID project for communication and distribution of results, day-to-day issues and formal threads. All of the TRIFFID's proposed means are listed here.

External communication and disseminations can be made through the project's website, social networks such as Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook and YouTube, quarterly news articles, leaflets and posters. An informed consent signed by the partners will be put in place for the use of partner images (such as logos, pictures, and others) linked to the project's communication and dissemination activities. This consent will be properly attached and detailed by the actions of WP1.

Internal communication will rely on the project's mailing lists, audio or teleconferences, and Google group chat or other preferred way of communication.

5.2.1. Project website

The official project website for project TRIFFID is available at <https://triffid-project.eu>.

There is a designated communication area on the TRIFFID's website where the dissemination WP will update the content with the most recent project news, including deliverables that have been formally submitted and authorized for public access, social network alerts, and other materials.

5.2.2. Mailing lists

At project start, key mailing lists have been created for facilitating project communication as management, as detailed in Table 5. Additional mail lists can/will be created, according to project needs

(e.g. at WP level), as the project evolves. As mentioned earlier, a spreadsheet with all the mailing lists created is maintained in the online repository at the “Supporting Documentation” location.

Table 5 TRIFFID mailing lists

Mailing list	Description	Partners involved
triffid-all@hua.gr	Mailing list for all consortium members	All partners
triffid-pmo@hua.gr	Mailing list for Project Management Office (PMO)	HUA
triffid-uc@hua.gr	Mailing list for use-cases, involving in principle the project end-users	GB, HFC, PUI, ROE, DCNA, HUA, UPC
triffid-tech@hua.gr	Mailing list for discussing technical issues, involving in principle the project technological partners	HUA, HMU, UPC, UWB, CNR, TEL, ITML
triffid-innov@hua.gr	Mailing list for discussing innovation-related issues, involving in principle the project academics, SME and LEs.	All partners

5.2.3. Audio and teleconference bridge

Teleconferences will be used by the TRIFFID consortium for internal communication, particularly for follow-up calls, internal project meetings and tracking work package status. The “Zoom” videotelephony platform will be used for this purpose, while any other available communication tool can be used by the TRIFFID consortium.

6. Quality assurance

6.1. Self-assessment

TRIFFID’s quality assurance and control will be carried out using a variety of techniques, such as self-evaluation, analysis of recent actions and outcomes, creation of the work plan for the following six months, and any modifications to the work plan. The PCC will make periodic use of these self-evaluation techniques, which will be reviewed at each project plenary meeting.

All action activities will be monitored in accordance with the “Plan-Do-Check-Act” (PDCA) iterative design and management method, taking into account all pertinent action details and the unique characteristics of EU collaborative actions, including internal action factors, such as the status of specific deliverables and milestones, and external action factors, such as changes in the relevant research and market areas.

Figure 9 The “Plan-Do-Check-Act” (PDCA) iterative design and management method

Project control will be carried out while taking into account a variety of internal project criteria, such as the status of the project’s deliverables and milestones, the overall development of the work, and the

status of the project's resources. On the other hand, many external circumstances (such as changes in the project's research and market areas) may have substantial impact on the project. These external factors will be continuously monitored by the PC and the TM. If required, corresponding corrective actions will be suggested and put into practice using the same guidelines.

6.2. Preparation of deliverables

A total of 33 deliverables will be submitted to the European Commission in the course of the TRIFFID project. In the followings, a set of guidelines for preparing deliverables is provided, in order to ensure timely and high-quality documents and other project material.

The deliverable template is maintained within the TRIFFID online repository (in the "Project TRIFFID\Supporting documentation\Templates" folder) and all deliverables should be adapted according to their specific characteristics. This template follows specific format and identity elements for the deliverable reports. All deliverables should be formed and adjusted accordingly taking this as a reference. Before releasing each deliverable, the deliverable responsible person must ensure that the correct template and format has been used and followed.

At the same time, a deliverable preparation plan has been developed, linked to project submission dates. The formal timeframe for deliverable preparation and submission is described in the table below.

Table 6 Timeframe for deliverable preparation

Days before the submission	Responsible person	Activity
60	WP/task/deliverable leader	Generate and upload deliverable template, notify contributing partners
45	WP/task/deliverable leader	Agree on the Table of Contents (ToC) with contributors and request their input
35	Contributors	Deadline for filling contributions
30	WP/task/deliverable leader	Check for completeness and consistency of contributors' input, request missing contributions and clarify potential inconsistencies
25	Contributors	Deadline for filling in additional contributions
20	WP/task/deliverable leader	Provide complete deliverable to 2 internal project reviewers and deliverable acceptance checklist
15	Internal project reviewers	Deadline for providing internal review to task/deliverable leader
10	WP/task/deliverable leader	Implement recommendations and comments from internal reviewers and share revised version for any final comments
5	Task/deliverable leader	Final version sent to PC and TM for final checking and approval
2	Project coordinator	Submission through the EC Web platform

6.3. Deliverables and internal reviewers

All project deliverables will be internally reviewed following a peer review methodology. The deliverables will be checked and approved by internal project reviewers prior to the submission to EC. Internal reviewers have been proposed by the PC and agreed with the consortium. Table 7 summarizes the deliverable responsible partners, the internal reviewers, as well as the delivery dates. Additionally,

the deliverable submission dates along TRIFFID’s Gantt chart is illustrated in Figure 10. To ensure the proper quality assessment of the deliverables, the internal reviewers will need to fill in the defined deliverable review evaluation form (stored in the TRIFFID online repository under the “Project TRIFFID\Supporting documentation\Templates”).

Table 7 Deliverables and internal reviewers

No.	Deliverable name	Lead	Type	Dis. level	Due date	Reviewer #1	Reviewer #2
D1.1	Project reference manual and quality plan	HUA	R	PU	M3	UPC	ITML
D1.2	Data management plan and IPR protection strategy 1	HUA	R	SEN	M6	GB	VUB
D1.3	Data management plan and IPR protection strategy 2	HUA	R	SEN	M36	GB	VUB
D1.4	Legal/ethical framework, societal impact assessment and innovation report 1	VUB	R	SEN	M8	DCNA	HUA
D1.5	Legal/ethical framework, societal impact assessment and innovation report 2	VUB	R	SEN	M18	DCNA	HUA
D1.6	Legal/ethical framework, societal impact assessment and innovation report 3	VUB	R	SEN	M36	DCNA	HUA
D2.1	End-user requirements 1	GB	R	SEN	M10	HUA	UPC
D2.2	End-user requirements 2	GB	R	SEN	M24	HUA	UPC
D2.3	Pilot scenarios and planning 1	PUI	R	SEN	M18	ITML	TEL
D2.4	Pilot scenarios and planning 2	PUI	R	SEN	M30	ITML	TEL
D2.5	Pilots execution, system acceptance and evaluation report	DCNA	DEM	SEN	M36	ITML	TEL
D3.1	Robot mission planning, navigation, safety and communications 1	UPC	R	PU	M15	CNR	UWB
D3.2	Robot mission planning, navigation, safety and communications 2	UPC	R	PU	M32	CNR	UWB
D4.1	Robot perception, EO analysis, HRI and HCI 1	HUA	R	PU	M15	UWB	HMU
D4.2	Robot perception, EO analysis, HRI and HCI 2	HUA	R	PU	M32	UWB	HMU
D5.1	Human factors analysis and participatory design toolkit	CNR	R	PU	M16	GB	PUI
D5.2	Optimal integration standards, protocols and policy recommendations 1	DCNA	R	PU	M24	HFC	ROE
D5.3	Optimal integration standards, protocols and policy recommendations 2	DCNA	R	PU	M36	GB	PUI
D5.4	Training curricula and exercises for first responders 1	DCNA	R	SEN	M22	HFC	ROE

7. Risk management

Due to the nature of research and innovation projects, risks are highly possible to occur during their lifetime and especially during their implementation phase. The term “risk” refers to an unexpected situation that may raise and create an impact on the project. Therefore, a dedicated risk management plan has been developed to prevent those issues or minimize their impact in case they happen. Potential risks that may emerge are related to technical risks, budget risks, business risks, etc. The best solution to monitor those risks is by following a thorough risk management approach.

TRIFFID’s success is highly dependent on the effectiveness of the risk management procedure. The main goal of this plan is to establish the main procedures and techniques for the constant evaluation and control of the potential risks, focusing on the on-time identification and appropriate handling.

The PC, in close collaboration with the PCC, is responsible for handling the risks and notifying the partners of any possible issues, as needed.

7.1. Risk methodology

TRIFFID’s risk methodology is mainly based on the Federation of European Risk Management Associations (FERMA¹) standards. This ongoing procedure is described through an iterative cycle which consists of five stages, aiming to ensure that risks are identified in a timely manner and are handled properly.

Figure 11 Risk management lifecycle

The effectiveness of the abovementioned practice depends on timely awareness and reaction to unexpected risk events and situations. Towards this end, a list of potential risks has already been identified for TRIFFID and will be constantly reviewed throughout the project’s duration.

¹ <https://www.ferma.eu/app/uploads/2011/11/a-risk-management-standard-english-version.pdf>

Table 8 presents the responsibility assignment matrix based on the RACI² model, which supports the following core roles:

- **Responsible (R):** The individual(s) with responsibility for the task or deliverable is responsible for developing and completing the project deliverables themselves. The responsible parties are typically hands-on team members who make direct contributions toward the completion of the project. The responsible team is composed of the project's doers, who work hands-on to ensure that each deliverable is completed.
- **Accountable (A):** Accountable parties ensure accountability to project deadlines, and ultimately, accountability to project completion. This group frequently also falls under the informed category.
- **Consulted (C):** Consulted individuals' opinions are crucial, and their feedback needs to be considered at every step of the game. These individuals provide guidance that is often a prerequisite to other project tasks, for example, providing legal guidance on a project throughout the process.
- **Informed (I):** Informed persons are those that need to stay in the loop of communication throughout the project. These individuals do not have to be consulted or be a part of the decision-making, but they should be made aware of all project updates.

Table 8 Responsibility assignment matrix for risk management

Phase	PC	TM	WPL	TL
Risk management approach	R	A	C	I
Risk identification	A	A	R	C
Risk assessment & analysis	A	A	R	C
Risk mitigation plan	A	A	R	C
Risk mitigation plan implementation	A	A	R	C
Risk tracking	A	A	R	C

As depicted in Table 8, for internal risks, TRIFFID's strategy is to use well-established methodologies for project planning and control. For example, the splitting of the project work into individual tasks and work packages minimizes the danger of internal risks. The PC will be mainly responsible for handling internal risks and inform all partners when necessary. On the other hand, the responsibility for the external risks involves directly and primarily the PCC committee. External risks will be decreased by following closely technological and business development in the field as well as on pertinent regulatory issues.

7.2. Risk identification

Identifying the risk is an important stage that will lead to its successful management. In the context of the TRIFFID project, the risks that will be documented are classified in the following categories:

- Administrative and organization risks, such as lack or shortage of availability of key resources, withdrawal of the participation of a partner having a key role, lack of communication,
- Technical risks, technology replacement issues, inadequate system integration, inadequate project results, and
- Business and exploitation risks, such as low interest of stakeholders, insufficient impact in standards liquidation of a partner business during the course of the project.

² <https://project-management.com/understanding-responsibility-assignment-matrix-raci-matrix/>

The partner/person who is assigned to monitor the risk is entitled as risk owner. The risk owner holds the responsibility for the next steps of the risk management practice until the resolution.

7.3. Risk assessment and analysis

After the identification of the risk, it should be analyzed and assessed in terms of defining the likelihood and consequence of occurrence. The level of likelihood of each risk is ranked on a five-point scale as depicted in Table 9.

Table 9 Risk level likelihood

Level	Likelihood	Probability
1	Not likely	~10%
2	Low likelihood	~30%
3	Likely	~50%
4	Highly likely	~70%
5	Near certainty	~90%

The level of consequence of each risk is established based on a number of criteria related to each particular situation. Examples include performance, schedule, cost, supportability, producibility and security. So, the overall impact severity is estimated as depicted in Table 10.

Table 10 Risk severity levels

Level	Likelihood
1	Negligible
2	Minor
3	Moderate
4	Significant
5	Severe

All partners are encouraged to contribute to the risk assessment procedure, by identifying risks and defining their nature. The collection and classification of the risks requires a detailed description and formulation in a unique matrix, which allows a doable methodical analysis. Table 11 defines a matrix for computing a risk “score”.

Table 11 Qualitative assessment of identified risks

		Severity				
		1	2	3	4	5
Likelihood	5	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	High
	4	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High	High
	3	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High
	2	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
	1	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate

The matrix in Table 11 is not symmetric and includes qualitative assessment of risk scores. In addition, Table 12 performs the mapping of the qualitative to quantitative risk assessments.

Table 12 Quantitative assessment of identified risks

Level	Probability	Definition
Low	<30%	Has little potential to cause disruption of schedule, increase in cost, or disruption of performance. Normal project effort will probably be able to overcome difficulties.
Moderate	30-69%	Can potentially cause some disruption of schedule, increase in cost, or disruption of performance. However, special effort will probably be able to overcome difficulties.
High	>70%	Likely to cause significant serious disruption of schedule, increase in cost, or degradation of performance.

7.4. Risk mitigation plan

In this phase, the objectives of the risk mitigation plan focus on the evaluation and selection of the best solutions/options that will lead to the minimization of the risk at acceptable levels. This can be achieved by decreasing the level of likelihood and the level of severity/consequence, or even better a combination of both. This plan should include the specifics of what should be done, when it should be accomplished, who is responsible, and the resources required for its implementation.

7.5. Risk mitigation plan implementation

The next activity constitutes the implementation of the risk mitigation plan, which functions as a key to a successful risk resolution. Specifically, it:

- Leads the partners towards the execution of the identified and agreed risk mitigation plans
- Summarizes the risks reporting requirements for an “in progress” monitoring
- Documents the history of changes

It is important that all implemented risk mitigation plans should be accomplished for each risk category through the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) level, before passing it up to the next WBS level.

7.6. Risk tracking

The final key activity entails systematic tracking and evaluation of the performance of risk mitigation actions. Risk tracking actually functions as a feedback procedure, where risk plans may be revised or updated based on risk status updates. If the plan is not effective, alternative plans must be put in place to ensure that the risk is appropriately handled. The PC is responsible for supervising the implementation of the risk management strategy and informing the consortium accordingly.

7.7. Risk registry

In the framework of the TRIFFID project, all identified risks should be registered in order to ensure their monitoring towards their mitigation. The main tool to monitor the identified risks is the “**Risk**

registry” that contains all information needed to assess and mitigate a risk and is available to all partner in the online repository at the “Risk registry” location.

For each identified risk, the risk registry shall detail (at least) the following key aspects:

- Risk ID number
- Risk description and category
- Risk origin (related WP and WPL)
- Log Date
- Last updated date
- Assessment
 - Likelihood
 - Severity
- Risk owner
- Risk status (Open / Occurred / Not occurred / Cancelled)
- Mitigation Plan
- Deadline for decision
- Progress/comments

During the grant preparation phase, a list of potential risks has already been identified; these are included in the GA document and also presented in Table 13. The risk registry will be populated, starting from the risks identified/mentioned in the GA.

Table 13 Risks identified during the grant preparation phase

Risks (Likelihood/Severity)	WPs	Mitigation measures
Management/Ethics risks		
Low quality of project results or too ambitious project objectives (MEDIUM/HIGH)	1, All	A thorough internal reviewing process for all project deliverables, activities and reports will ensure high quality results and timely identification of targeted quality deviations. Project objectives will be revisited periodically by the GA, while external experts from the Advisory Board will act as a corrective body.
Delays in task completion or disharmony in partner collaboration (LOW/MEDIUM)	1, All	The work plan of the project has been carefully defined and the partners have a lot of experience in participating in R&D projects. The management team will adopt a proactive approach, by identifying all critical paths in the project and rescheduling if necessary.
Processing of data from which sensitive information can be inferred (LOW/HIGH)	1, All	Relevant guidelines will be established early in the project (T1.3), based on applicable laws/regulations, and their implementation will be continuously monitored. If necessary, privacy-preserving methods will be deployed (e.g, face de-identification).
Technical/Acceptance risks		
Difficulties to integrate robotic solutions into FR operational procedures; user acceptance issues (MEDIUM/HIGH)	2, 5	A continuous monitoring approach shall ensure early focus on related acceptability challenges. Human-centered design and active participation of stakeholders to system definition development will ensure focus on user needs (T2.1, T5.2). The AMRs will have clearly defined roles/functionalities and be integrated as support technology; not as replacements of human FRs.
Inefficiency of the employed hardware to	6	The project UCs have been thoroughly analyzed so as to clearly identify the particularities of the selected application cases and

meet application requirements (LOW/MEDIUM)		inform the selection and integration of hardware components. In case any issues arise, T6.1 will identify suitable alternatives to serve as backup solutions for T6.2, while robotics partners will proceed with research using their existing owned equipment until all issues are resolved.
Project DNNs do not achieve specified performance due to lack of sufficient training data (MEDIUM/HIGH)	4	Efforts of relevant partners will intensify for exploiting properly adjusted public datasets and end-user data, manually constructing new annotated datasets, as well as employing transfer learning, data augmentation and photorealistic simulators to derive synthetic data. Additionally, AI methods for data augmentation from T4.1 will be exploited to circumvent any remaining issues.
Errors in robotic planning due to insufficient background knowledge or imprecise environment interpretation (MEDIUM/HIGH)	3	The components developed for handling robotic planning activities have dependencies on multiple other system modules and procedures, while also being prone to facing runtime difficulties in the real experimental setting. Thus, module integration, deployment and evaluation will be of high priority from the early stages of the project.
Risks stemming from failure of the safety management module (MEDIUM/MEDIUM)	3	Relevant notifications will allow the Ground-Station Operator to manually override autonomous robot operation, including the safety management module, in case of failure.
Some AMR methods do not satisfy all system requirements at the specified TRL (e.g., regarding accuracy or speed) (MEDIUM/MEDIUM)	3, 4	Alternative algorithms or hardware modifications will be tried.
The AR interface proves too cumbersome for humans (MEDIUM/LOW)	4	Care will be taken to make all Ground-Station functionalities also available through a mouse-operated Web interface, even at the cost of reduced immersion.
Other risks		
The exploitation plan seems ineffective (LOW/HIGH)	6	Specific actions and proactive behaviors are foreseen in WP7, as part of the overall exploitation plan, to ensure that, during project lifetime, all partners remain aligned with the committed individual plans, while constant monitoring, control of the planned activities and consistent internal reporting in periodic meetings will be performed as well.
Stakeholders outside the project are not interested (MEDIUM/MEDIUM)	7	Stakeholders will be contacted early in the project, through the various communication activities to raise interest throughout the scientific and end-user communities.

8. Innovation management

8.1. Rationale

As a research and development project of the Horizon Europe program, the primary objective of the TRIFFID project is the development of highly innovative solutions. The primary axes for innovation are defined in the TRIFFID proposal, encompassing both technical and organizational innovations. Therefore, the efforts and activities of the TRIFFID project are contributing, directly or indirectly, to the generation of innovations. In this way, the TRIFFID project differs from conventional organizations that require specific steps to generate and manage innovations. In the TRIFFID project, innovation will therefore be realized by the entire project team and the entire project management teams contribute to innovation management.

For this reason, this section will focus on describing additional measures to support the project in realizing its innovation objectives and optimizing its innovation potential.

8.2. Approach

The ISO56000 family of standards³, developed by ISO/TEC 279, proposes a framework to guide organizations engaging in innovation activities. While theoretically applicable to all types of organizations, the approach to innovation management presented is clearly geared towards larger organizations, whose primary activity is not the generation of innovation. The particular nature of the TRIFFID project, which is entirely focused on innovation, renders a number of aspects (for instance about organizational culture as a facilitator for innovation) irrelevant.

The framework of the ISO56000 family of standards is therefore only used as a flexible guidance for the definition of an innovation management strategy. This section follows the definition used in ISO56000:2021 “Innovation Management – Fundamentals and vocabulary”, notably the definition of innovation as a “new or changed entity realizing or redistributing value” with entity understood as “anything perceivable or conceivable “for instance “a product, service, process, model, method... or a combination thereof”. The following sections will formulate the high-level innovation vision, a consistent innovation strategy and will present activities to realize the high-level objective of the strategy.

8.3. Vision, objective, strategy, activities

8.3.1. Innovation vision and objectives

Due to its innovative nature, the TRIFFID project overall strategy and objectives can be considered as primary innovation objectives. In particular, a list of targeted innovations is detailed in the GA under

³ In particular, ISO 56000:2021 “Innovation Management – Fundamentals and vocabulary”, ISO56002:2019 “Innovation Management – Innovation Management Systems – Guidance” and ISO 56003:2021 “Innovation Management – Tools and Methods for Innovation partnerships – Guidance”

the list of “Expected results”, most of which can be considered as an “innovation”, while additional ones can be generated during the project execution.

Producing the above-mentioned primary innovations is the responsibility of the entire project team and is managed directly by the IM. In particular, the **first objective** of the IM’s activity is to support and advise the project team, focusing on facilitating the path to exploitation of the primary innovations of the TRIFFID project.

The TRIFFID project aims at maximizing its impact, among others, by fully exploiting its innovation potential. In innovative projects such as TRIFFID, such innovations are frequently achieved as a by-product of the process of achieving the primary innovations, but sometimes cannot be perceived as such and, hence not, exploited. The **second objective** of the IM’s activities is to facilitate the discovery of such secondary “low-hanging fruits” innovations and to support the path to exploitation.

Overall, the innovation strategy and activities should provide inputs to the exploitation and take-up activities of the TRIFFID project (including maturity assessment and IP status) and appropriately influence the development of innovation items to facilitate their exploitation.

8.3.2. Strategy and activities

Following the innovation vision and objectives, the innovation strategy will rely on two main axes. The first axis will aim at ensuring that primary innovations are ready for the exploitation activities and the second axis will target to uncover potential secondary innovations and to ensure their exploitation when relevant. Additionally, transverse activities will be carried out to support the execution of the activities in the two primary axes.

8.3.2.1. Innovation strategy axis #1: Monitoring and assessing the primary innovations

The first axis is targeting the primary innovations. In this axis, the IM’s activities will be monitoring the critical innovative characteristics of the primary innovations developed in the TRIFFID project to ensure that the innovations are ready to enter exploitation activities. In this sense, the IM’s activities will serve as an input for the exploitation activities. Note that the technical management of the development is the responsibility of the TM, not of the IM.

The following characteristics will be assessed (and revised as necessary, following the development cycle):

- Status of the innovation in terms of Intellectual Property: e.g., foreground of a single partner, joint foreground, relevant background, etc.
- Maturity level of the innovation, using the appropriate Technology Readiness Level scale and process
- Existence and type of potential relevant third-party IP required by the innovations
- Alignment with the environment in which the innovation is expected to be deployed. Depending on the nature of the innovation this can be a technical environment, an organizational environment, etc.
- Need for IPR protection measures and, if relevant, available options

The initial activities will be consolidated (requiring a collaboration among the TM, the IM and the remaining technical partners) into a list of expected primary innovations.

Further, the following activities will be carried out every 3 months (adaptable per innovation, based on the respective development advancement):

- Assessment of the characteristics of the innovations as mentioned in the previous paragraph: IP status, maturity, required third-party IP, alignment with the environment, need for IPR protection measures.
- When appropriate, proposition for actions regarding the maturity level, alignment with the environment provided to the TM and relevant partners.
- When appropriate, proposition for actions regarding IPR protection measures and initiation of exploitation or uptake actions provided to the PC, the TM and the relevant technological partners.

8.3.2.2. Innovation strategy axis #2: Uncovering potential secondary innovations

TRIFFID (as an innovative project) defines primary innovations during the proposal phase. However, experience in this type of projects shows that other innovations or low-hanging opportunities frequently appear in the course of the execution of the project. Appropriate IM's activities will facilitate towards identifying potential secondary innovations and supporting the paths to exploitation.

While many sources of secondary innovation may exist, the TRIFFID innovation strategy will particularly address the following:

- Innovations that are made as intermediate steps of the development of primary innovations. Partners and teams involved in the development are often focused on the primary innovation and frequently do not spontaneously recognize the potential value of intermediate steps. Support from the IM' can boost the identification.
- Combining primary innovations or (intermediate steps) can lead to secondary innovations. Teams involved in the development can benefit from the support of the IM's activities.
- Primary and secondary innovations may be re-used (with or without adaptation) to support multiple capabilities or the same capabilities in different application domains. The IM's activities can facilitate the developing teams with the identification of new opportunities.

Uncovering (potential) secondary innovations requires a high degree of specialized knowledge and understanding of the primary innovation and the application domain. The practices to be used should allow leverage of experience, novel ideas and the stakeholders' knowledge in order to identify, develop, and implement the most valuable secondary innovations opportunities. The activities implemented will therefore rely on the entire project teams, with the IM serving as a facilitator for the reflection. The following activities are envisioned:

- Leverage the monitoring activities and assessment of primary innovations described in Section 8.3.2.1 to discuss the intermediate steps, potential combination and reuse with the partner(s) developing the innovations.
- Leverage project-wide meetings, and in particular demonstration and test sessions for brainstorming/ innovation workshops, including detection of connections (i.e., relationships with other relevant projects). These sessions should engage the entire project team including end-users to identify new capabilities and applications that could be easily addressed.
- Immediately after the main project demonstration and test events, specific (on-line or F2F) sessions will be organized with the end-user group to uncover exploitation opportunities that are beyond the particular scope of the project.

When the above discussions lead to candidates' innovations, the results of these discussions will trigger actions from the IM's side to:

- Refine the identification of the candidates and involve all stakeholders (particularly when the secondary innovation is the result of a combination)
- Validate the potential by
 - Initiating the research on state-of-art (that will have to be carried out by the developing partners due to the highly specialized knowledge required)
 - Examining and evaluating the environment requirements for the innovation to be viable with support of the domain experts of TRIFFID.

If the potential of the candidate secondary innovation is validated, it will then enter the process followed for primary innovations (Section 8.3.2.1).

8.3.2.3. Innovation strategy supporting activities

The IM's acts will incorporate supporting activities targeting the two axes of the innovation strategy and supporting the stakeholders developing innovations (e.g., the project team).

The supporting activities will include the development of resources, in particular:

- Resources facilitating the assessment of maturity, including explanatory material and lightweight assessment material.
- Resources facilitating the assessment of IP status.
- Resources supporting partners in their reflection on IPR protection measures and options.
- High level resources supporting the awareness of the state-of-the-art and connected innovations in particular resulting from other EC supported research and innovation actions. More specialized resources will be provided by the partners in their area of expertise. These resources will be used as driver for discussion and brainstorming sessions aiming at discovering secondary innovations.

The alignment of technical choices among various innovations generated by the project and with best practices in the relevant environment is a known and important facilitator of exploitation and uptake. While the (technical) development choices remain the responsibilities of the partners and are supervised by the TM, the IM will provide support and advice when relevant, regarding the opportunities for unification and normalization within the project and with developments outside of the project. When appropriate, collaboration with appropriate external bodies and organizations will be established to investigate the potential for standardization activities. The IM will incorporate activities pertaining to the monitoring of the innovations in the domain of disaster management and first responder activities in generally. While the IM will execute generic monitoring and evaluation of results from other projects supported by the EC, these activities will also be supported by a) the partners developing innovation items for the specialized aspects pertaining to their innovation, and b) the end-users as domain experts.

8.3.3. Roles

As already noted, the TRIFFID project is inherently an "Innovation Activity". The core of the innovation activities is carried out by the partners themselves in their development of the innovation items. These activities are coordinated and supervised by the PC and the TM.

The activities connected with the IM, as described in Section 8.3.2, will be performed in collaboration with and reporting to the PC and the TM. The IM is responsible for providing supporting resources,

organizing and facilitating activities and assessments, continuous monitoring and reporting to the PC. Maturity assessments will be a collaborative activity led and facilitated by the IM and involving the partner(s) producing the innovation items and the TM. Such activities will involve the partners producing the individual innovation items, e.g., the entire project team. Moreover, the IM will provide input for and contribute to the market analysis and development of business models activities of the project.

8.4. Intellectual property rights

The management of intellectual property is a critical aspect of the innovation management process. Two aspects should be distinguished:

- The IP status of an innovation item e.g., the ownership of an innovation item produced by the project and the status of its dependencies
- The appropriate means to protect the IPRs of the owner of an innovation item

The IM will support and advise the partners by determining the IP status of the innovation items produced, distinguishing foreground, joint foreground and required background and record the decisions. When applicable, advice can be provided to the stakeholders in determining the required permissions or access rights to background and possible licensing schemes. The TRIFFID project CA constitutes the leading reference point to interpret and advise partners with respect to the definition of ownerships, access rights and permissions.

Innovation items consisting of software frequently rely on third-party libraries, whose IP-status/licensing scheme may influence the status of the innovation items themselves. The IM will foster the investigation of the status of third-party items incorporated in or required by their innovation items and support the monitoring thereof. The use of automatic tools will be encouraged and accompanied. The TRIFFID project's envisioned GitLab will serve as the main tool for both CI/CD development and code repositories. GitLab incorporates the tool "LicenceFinder" to facilitate project teams to automatically detect and flag licenses or dependencies.

Upon request, the IM will advise on the appropriate means to protect the IPR owner for a given innovation item. Different schemes will be envisioned depending on the nature of the innovation item and the exploitation path foreseen by the owner, including patenting (strong but expensive protection) and publication as open-source software with a wide range of licenses with different characteristics (more or less restrictive). Such a decision is strongly intertwined with exploitation/business-model planning activities of the project.

8.5. Maturity level of generated innovations

As an RnD project, TRIFFID aims at producing innovations items of high maturity. The Technological Readiness Level (TRL) scale has been adopted by the EC since 2010 and is highly suggested to be used by its funded projects. Within TRIFFID, continuous assessment of the TRL levels of each individual components will facilitate the project team to develop novel tools or to advance already existing one.

Figure 12 Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale

In practice, the generic definition of TRLs should be operationalized for the specific nature of the innovation items in the specific project domain. The IM will provide guidance and resources for this operationalization and will provide a lightweight guide suitable for the evaluation in the context of the TRIFFID project. In particular, many of the innovation items envisioned in the TRIFFID project are software items. The IM will use the operationalization process proposed by the US army for software components⁴. Additionally, many of the envisioned innovation items incorporate AI/ML components, for which the direct interpretation of the TRL level is difficult. The IM will rely on the technical report⁵ published by the EC's Joint Research Centre (JRC), which provides an example-based methodology for the assessment of AI technologies. The assessment will be carried out jointly by the relevant partners, the TM and the IM.

4

https://asc.army.mil/docs/pubs/alt/2004/3_MayJun/articles/10_Use_of_Tech_Readiness_Levels_for_Software_Dev_200403.pdf

⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/cb8f38a9-3385-11eb-b27b-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

9. Conclusions

This deliverable described all managerial procedures related to TRIFFID's preference reference manual and quality plan, where defined item and process has been guided by appropriate quality considerations (from both a technical and management perspective) for meeting the project goals and objectives.

The management procedures and choices included in this document have resulted after thorough discussions with project partners. To this end, the current deliverable will serve as the overall governing document of TRIFFID. Together with the CA, this document comprises the framework for guiding partner collaboration and communication across all project aspects. Moreover, the current document may be updated/adapted in the future, according to possible future project needs.